

Advanced Techniques for Digital Nonlinear Compensation in Multi-carrier Optical Transmission Systems

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Abstract: High-capacity optical communications are currently evolving towards multi-carrier transmission. We review the new challenges and opportunities for digital nonlinear mitigation in these systems, optimizing the performance versus complexity trade-off.

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1. Recent Trends on Multi-Carrier Optical Transmission

The continuous growth of traffic demand in optical core networks is currently pushing both optics and electronics to the technology limits [1]. After the standardization of transmission/detection technologies for 100G optical channels, firm steps have already been taken towards the standardization of 400G optical transmission [3], with 1 Tb/s coming as the next-generation solution for high-capacity and long-haul optical links [4]. Due to the electronic limitations at the transceiver side, a new concept of optical superchannels [5] has emerged, making use of multiple optical carriers that are individually generated but jointly routed through the optical network as a single entity, thereby relaxing the electronic bandwidth requirements on critical components such as analog-to-digital (ADC) and digital-to-analog converters (DAC) [6]. Although the research on ultra-high-speed single-carrier transmission also remains as a very active topic [7], the deployment of 400G is most likely to be based on dual-, triple- or even quad-carrier transceivers, with varying modulation formats and symbol-rates, depending on the compromise between spectral efficiency and maximum reach [8]. Meanwhile, the research on future 1 Tb/s optical channels is already on the rise, in which case the plethora of possible solutions is likely to be even larger.

2. Nonlinear Mitigation Techniques for Optical Superchannels

It is well known that the Kerr-related nonlinear distortions are the ultimate fiber capacity limiting factor, setting the optimum usable per-channel power and consequently the maximum signal reach [9]. To counteract this limitation, several digital nonlinear mitigation techniques have been proposed in the last decade, attracting a significant research interest [10–15]. Among the vast number of methods and algorithms, the most disseminated techniques are based on the concept of digital backpropagation (DBP) [10, 11]. Although DBP has shown the potential of increasing the maximum signal reach by over 20% [16], its practical implementation is still lacking two major features: i) fast estimation of fiber parameters and ii) feasible complexity for implementation in a real-time hardware platform. Taking advantage of the superchannel concept, several recent works have exploited the enhanced performance enabled by multi-carrier DBP, demonstrating more than 80% reach extension in the limit of single superchannel transmission [17]. However, the natural extension of DBP to multi-carrier transmission based on a full-field approach comes at the expense of increased complexity, bringing DBP computational effort far beyond the limits of state-of-the-art electronics [18]. Advanced techniques are therefore required to exploit the full potential of DBP applied to optical superchannels [19], improving the tradeoff between complexity and performance.

3. Nonlinear Mitigation in Subcarrier Multiplexing Systems

A different flavour of multi-carrier transmission based on subcarrier multiplexing (SCM) has recently started to attract significant attention [20–23], mostly due to the inherent nonlinear mitigation phenomenon that is enabled by symbol-rate optimization (SRO) [22, 23]. In SCM systems, each optical channel is subdivided into low symbol-rate subcarriers (typically 2–4 Gbaud), which are electronically generated by the same transceiver. Besides the large number of simulation and analytical results, some recent works have shown experimental evidence of the SRO effect, enabling >10% extended reach without requiring any digital signal processing overhead for nonlinear mitigation [21].

In addition, it has been recently shown that the effects of SRO and DBP can be combined together [24], thereby maximizing the system performance. The very-low symbol-rates associated with the SCM technique also dramatically change the physical phenomena occurring during signal propagation in fiber, creating new opportunities for the application of low-complexity DBP.

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